

The Effect of Ambient Conditions on the Potential Screening at Ionic Liquid – Electrode Interfaces

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ABSTRACT

In comparison to the clean conditions of ultrahigh vacuum (UHV), we investigate the influence of ambient conditions on the potential screening (PS) at the interfaces of Au and Pt electrodes with the ionic liquids $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$. Our study is based on a proof-of-principle experiment that shows that PS measurements performed by XPS yield the same results as measurements using a specific 3-electrode sample holder setup, both in UHV. Based on this, we compare PS measurements under ultraclean conditions by XPS with PS measurements with a 3-electrode setup in N_2 and in air. We demonstrate that there is indeed an influence of the ambient gas atmosphere, which depends on applied voltage and combination of IL and electrode material. For Pt electrodes, there is a pronounced influence of the ambient conditions on the PS for both $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$, while for Au electrodes hardly any influence is seen. We attribute the observed effects mainly to water affecting the electrical double layers at the IL/electrode interfaces. In addition, we observe that reaction products formed under faradaic conditions can lead to a contamination of the 3rd electrode (reference electrode), yielding time-dependent deviations from the true behavior.

Introduction

Ionic liquids (ILs) represent a significant innovation for electrochemical applications. Due to the great tunability of their physicochemical properties, these molten salts can be well adapted for electrodeposition (Abbott and McKenzie, 2006, Wibowo et al., 2011, Endres, 2002), supercapacitor (Wang et al., 2017, Van Aken et al., 2015, Lian et al., 2018) and battery (Osada et al., 2016, Karimi et al., 2021) technologies. Due to their often wider electrochemical window compared to aqueous or organic electrolytes, ILs are particularly suitable to achieve higher energy densities in electrochemical devices. However, impurities can drastically affect their physicochemical properties and electrochemical performance. When working under ambient conditions, water is expected to be the main contamination, since ILs are typically hygroscopic; even hydrophobic ILs can rapidly absorb water if exposed to ambient humidity (Wasserscheid and Welton, 2008). Already small mole fractions of water can cause a decrease in viscosity and weaken the electrostatic interactions between cations and anions (Seddon et al., 2000, Ridings et al., 2011). In electrochemistry, cyclic voltammetry (CV) studies of various ILs have shown a pronounced reduction of the electrochemical window with the increase of relative humidity (Doblinger et al., 2020). Dissolved water in ILs can induce additional features in CVs, which can have comparable intensity than those of the electroactive species under study

(Silvester and Compton, 2006). Moreover, decomposition reactions of IL ions, such as $[\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]^-$, can be catalyzed by the presence of water and OH^- (Howlett et al., 2006).

While the effect of residual water in ILs has been extensively studied for faradaic reactions, its influence at the liquid-solid interface and in particular on the structure of the electrical double layer (EDL) in non-faradaic situations such as in supercapacitors has been investigated much less. Molecular dynamics simulations showed that impurity water molecules accumulate within a subnanometer thick layer at the charged electrodes, and that the accumulated amount increases with increasing voltage (Feng et al., 2014). Hence, the electrical properties of the EDL can be strongly affected even by a small bulk concentration of water molecules, because small changes in local ion density can considerably change the potential drop across the IL/electrode interface (Feng et al., 2014). Force curve studies at the $\text{Au}(111)/[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Pyrr}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ interface performed with atomic force microscopy (AFM) showed a decreasing stiffness of the interfacial layering of the IL with increasing water concentration (Zhong et al., 2016). These findings were attributed either to adsorption of water molecules at the electrode, or to weakening the attraction between IL cations and anions, thereby modifying the layered structure close to the electrodes. Another AFM force curve study revealed alterations on the layering at the liquid/solid interface given by water also for an imidazolium-based IL ($[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$) on Au

PS, Potential Screening; UHV, Ultrahigh Vacuum; XPS, X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy; EDL, Electrical Double Layer.

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electrodes; these changes were mainly attributed to the interaction of water with the ionic moieties of the IL while pronounced adsorption effects of water at the polarized Au electrodes were not observed (Cheng et al., 2015). From the mentioned studies, it is evident that different interactions between the components of the system involved (ions, contaminants, electrode surface, applied potential) contribute to the observed behavior. Thus, it is of great importance to compare the interaction of various ILs with different electrode materials under ultraclean conditions and ambient conditions. Moreover, since purifying and degassing of ILs might be costly and not always a feasible choice for large-scale applications, the characterization of the influence of contaminations on such systems is of great interest in order to find out the best operation condition when using ILs under ambient conditions without additional processing.

In this study, we focus on the effect of ambient conditions on the interface of ILs and different metal electrodes. We do this by investigating the potential screening (PS) behavior in air and also in a N_2 atmosphere (as model system with a low water content) in comparison to reference measurements under ultraclean (contamination-free) conditions. For the latter, we use X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) under ultrahigh vacuum (UHV) conditions in a symmetric 2-electrode setup; the advantages of this approach and experimental details are outlined in our previous work (Greco et al., 2019). In these experiments, we measured XPS binding energy (BE) shifts of IL-related core levels as a function of the applied voltage U_{applied} . Thereby, the observed behavior is characteristic for a particular IL/electrode combination (Greco et al., 2019). Thus, the BE vs U_{applied} curves can be used as fingerprints, which proved to be particularly valuable to deduce information on the PS and EDL composition at the polarized electrode interfaces of IL mixtures (Shin et al., 2021). Herein, we now extend this approach to compare PS curves recorded in UHV by XPS with PS curves in 1 bar N_2 gas or in 1 bar air using a 3-electrode setup (for details, see below). Notably, XPS cannot be performed at 1 bar, and thus only 3-electrode PS measurements can be realized under these conditions. From the comparison, conclusions on the influence of contaminations on the PS can be derived: On the one hand, if the PS curves recorded in N_2 or air show the same behavior as in UHV, we can assume that contaminants do not have any significant effect on the PS. On the other hand, different PS curves arising from different measuring environments indicate an alteration of the PS by contaminations. The comparison of measurements in N_2 and in air provides some indication on the sensitivity of the PS and thus also the EDL to contaminations introduced by the surrounding gas atmosphere.

In the following, we first verify that PS measurements performed by XPS in UHV yield the same results as measurements using a very specific 3-electrode sample holder in UHV. Based on this proof-of-principle experiment, we then compare PS measurements by XPS in UHV with PS measurements with a 3-electrode setup performed in N_2 and in air, and simultaneously record the cell current between working and counter electrode. With these measurements, we demonstrate that there is indeed an influence of the gas atmosphere, which depends on applied voltage and the combination of IL and electrode material. By adding excess of water in a 1:1 water-IL solution, we will demonstrate that the contamination effect on PS is mainly due to water. In the course of our studies, we also observed that for certain IL/electrode combinations reaction products formed under faradaic conditions lead to a contamination of the 3rd reference electrode, yielding time-dependent deviations from the true behavior.

Results and Discussion

Experimental concept and comparison of PS measurements using XPS in UHV and using a 3rd reference electrode in UHV

In the following, the link between the 2-electrode XPS and 3-electrode PS measurements will be detailed in Fig. 1 for non-faradaic conditions (that is, negligible residual current after charging), both in

UHV. As described previously for our 2-electrode setup (Greco et al., 2019), an external voltage U_{applied} is applied between two identical electrodes (that is, same metal and same electrolyte/electrode contact area); the grounded electrode is the counter electrode (CE) and the non-grounded one is the working electrode (WE). Due to U_{applied} , the ions of the IL rearrange at the liquid/metal interfaces to compensate for the electrode charges forming EDLs, yielding corresponding potential drops $\Delta\phi$ at the two electrodes (note that due to the high ion density in ILs, the potential drops for moderate applied voltages predominantly occur within the first IL interface layer by accumulation of the corresponding counter ions (Castillo et al., 2012, Baldelli, 2013), while no potential drop takes place in the bulk between the two electrodes, when faradaic currents are absent). Consequently, the potential of the IL bulk shifts (Fig. 1) relative to CE, which can be measured with XPS by recording one of the IL core levels: at a certain applied voltage, U_{applied} , the binding energy difference (ΔBE) relative to the BE at $U_{\text{applied}} = 0$ V gives access to the potential drop changes at the interfaces ($e\Delta\phi$). In the example illustrated in Fig. 1, ΔBE is equal to the potential drop at the anode ($e\Delta\phi_{\text{anodic}}$), since the grounded CE is positively polarized and attracts the anions of the IL while $\Delta\phi_{\text{cathodic}} = U_{\text{applied}} - \Delta\phi_{\text{anodic}}$ is the potential drop at the WE (cathode) (Greco et al., 2019).

Since XPS requires UHV conditions, the measurements in N_2 and air must be carried out in a different way, which we realize by recording the potential change (ΔV_{ref}) of a 3rd inert reference electrode that is connected to CE via a high resistance multimeter (>10 G Ω) (see Supporting Information and Figs. S1 and S2 for further details). As shown in Fig. 1, ΔV_{ref} recorded at $U_{\text{applied}} = -2$ V relative to $U_{\text{applied}} = 0$ V is equal to $\Delta\phi_{\text{anodic}}$. To test the suitability of both methods, we performed proof-of-principle PS measurements in UHV with both types of the setup (2-electrode configuration with XPS (yielding ΔBE), 3-electrode setup (yielding ΔV_{ref}) by using the molybdenum support sample holder as 3rd reference electrode). Note that due to the high resistance of the multimeter (>10 G Ω), the measured potential changes ΔV_{ref} are expected to be independent of the choice of the 3rd electrode material. For these experiments, we used an IL/electrode combination with a very characteristic ΔBE vs U_{applied} behavior, namely $[C_8C_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}/\text{Pt}$. As shown in Fig. 2, ΔBE and ΔV_{ref} show exactly the same variation with U_{applied} , that is, ΔBE is equal to $e\Delta V_{\text{ref}}$. Since both methods agree well under UHV conditions, we can assert that our use of a 3rd reference electrode is suitable to measure PS also in N_2 atmosphere and air. All the ΔV_{ref} measurements are recorded for negative and positive polarization relative to both the WE and CE over time (Supporting Information Figs. S3 to S6) and both $\Delta\phi_{\text{anodic}}$ and $\Delta\phi_{\text{cathodic}}$ are obtained. This is particularly useful to detect modifications at the electrodes and in the electrochemical cell during the measurements. Again, $\Delta\phi_{\text{anodic}} + \Delta\phi_{\text{cathodic}}$ is always equal to U_{applied} and thus, $\Delta\phi_{\text{anodic}}$ can be always converted to $\Delta\phi_{\text{cathodic}}$ ($\Delta\phi_{\text{cathodic}} = U_{\text{applied}} - \Delta\phi_{\text{anodic}}$). In the next sections, the averages of the absolute values in the four quadrants (Fig. 2) are shown as the $\Delta\phi_{\text{cathodic}}$ curves for a clearer presentation; the error bars indicate the standard errors.

As a final remark, our 3-electrode PS method can of course be related to a typical 3-electrode setup consisting also of WE, CE and reference electrode (RE). In such a standard potentiostatic configuration, however, the WE is the electrode at which the potential relative to a high-ohmic RE is *controlled* via a potentiostat, that is, the applied voltage U_{applied} between WE and CE is continuously adapted such to achieve a certain desired potential drop ΔV_{ref} between WE and RE. In our setup, a *constant* potential difference U_{applied} of choice is applied between WE and CE employing a potential source (as it is done e.g. in a supercapacitor application), and ΔV_{ref} is only read through the high resistance circuit via a high resistance multimeter.

$[C_8C_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}/\text{Au}/\text{Au}$

Fig. 3a compares the $\Delta\phi_{\text{cathodic}}$ curves of $[C_8C_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ for two identical Au electrodes measured in UHV, and in N_2 and air using a Pt wire as

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the EDL structure and the potential at the interface for the electrochemical cell comprised of $[C_8C_1Im]Cl$ and two identical Pt electrodes. The respective XPS spectra of the N 1s region are reported on the left, indicating the BE and the ΔBE for 0V and -2V applied. The $e\Delta\phi_{anodic}$ indicates the potential drop measured against the CE for -2V applied and is equal to ΔV_{ref} and ΔV_{ref} .

Fig. 2. Relation between the ΔBE (N 1s) and the ΔV_{ref} measured with a 3rd reference electrode for the electrochemical cell comprised of $[C_8C_1Im]Cl$ and two identical Pt electrodes vs an applied voltage. The black symbols correspond to the curves measured in UHV with XPS, the red symbols to the curves measured in UHV with a 3rd reference electrode. The dashed straight (± 0.5 eV/V) lines indicate equal potential drop at the cathode and anode interface.

3rd reference electrode; Pt as noble metal was chosen to avoid changes in $\Delta\phi$ at this reference electrode due to the ambient conditions (e.g. surface oxidation by air). The data determined in UHV by XPS (black squares) are reproduced from (Greco et al., 2019). They exhibit a linear behavior with a slope of 0.92 V/V that is nearly twice the slope of 0.50 V/V (dashed line) of an ideal symmetric behavior, where half of the applied voltage is each screened at the cathodic and the anodic sides. The observed highly asymmetric behavior of $\Delta\phi_{cathodic}$ indicates that most of the PS takes place at the cathodic side while at the anodic side the PS is small. In our previous studies, we assigned this behavior to the large size difference between the $[C_8C_1Im]^+$ cation and the Cl^- anion (Greco et al., 2019, Shin et al., 2021). In a simple Helmholtz approximation for ILs under non-faradaic conditions, $\Delta\phi$ at an electrode is

Fig. 3. a) Cathodic voltage of $[C_8C_1Im]Cl$ vs $U_{applied}$ between two identical Au electrodes. The black line refers to the measurements performed in UHV with XPS, red and blue lines refer to the measurements performed with a 3rd reference electrode in N_2 and air atmosphere, respectively. The dashed straight line (± 0.5 V/V) indicates equal PS at the cathode and the anode. b) Averaged currents recorded during the measurements.

inversely proportional to the corresponding EDL capacitance and – due to the identical contact areas in our setup – directly proportional to the size of the counterions. Hence, at the cathode, the large imidazolium cations lead to a large $\Delta\varphi_{\text{cathodic}}$, which is considerably larger than the small $\Delta\varphi_{\text{anodic}}$ at the anode resulting from the smaller chloride anions.

To investigate the influence of ambient conditions on the PS characteristics, we performed PS measurements in N_2 and in air (red and blue symbols in Fig. 3) using a Pt wire as a 3rd reference electrode. Surprisingly, the cathodic voltage curves are virtually identical to the measurements performed in UHV. Following our fingerprint approach, the N_2 and air atmospheres lead to the same asymmetric PS behavior as in UHV (the small differences at 2 V are within the experimental uncertainty). At first sight, this unchanged asymmetric behavior directly indicates an unchanged composition of the EDL which is solely given by the dissimilar sizes of cations and anions of the IL. However, considering the fact that the behavior is dominated by the large cations, yielding a slope of 0.92 V/V, small changes at the anodic side (e.g. via adsorption of other small ions such as OH^-) would also leave the behavior unchanged. Fig. 3b depicts the measured steady-state currents between cathode and anode recorded during the PS measurements under the three different conditions. In UHV, the current is negligible up to the highest voltage of 2 V, indicating that faradaic phenomena at the electrode interface are absent under the ultra-clean conditions of UHV. On the contrary, in N_2 and air (red and blue symbols, respectively), the current rises above 0.5 V applied voltage, indicating that faradaic reactions start to take place at these voltages; notably, this current increase is much more pronounced in air than in N_2 , while it does not have an impact on the PS behavior. Therefore, for this particular IL/electrode combination, faradaic reactions do not seem to affect the observed PS, which is an indication that the composition of the corresponding EDLs do not change significantly due to the presence of N_2 or air. We propose that the residence time of formed redox products at the electrodes that are generated at voltages above 0.5 V is small compared to the time scale of our averaging PS measurements, which “see” predominantly Cl^- and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]^+$ as counterions at the interfaces. At the anode, the dominant presence of Cl^- on Au at the expense of other species formed in course of the oxidation is not surprising: pronounced adsorption of halides at the Au surface in contact with IL mixtures was found even in cases where these halide anions were only present in traces (Shin et al., 2021, Hayes et al., 2012). As final comment, one should note that despite the fact that the PS curves and therefore the EDLs are not significantly affected by contaminations, the observed faradaic currents occurring in N_2 atmosphere and air could lead to issues such as discharging effects in IL-based supercapacitor applications.

$[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}/\text{Pt}/\text{Pt}$

The electrode material plays a crucial role in the structure of the EDL. In contrast to the previous example of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ and Au electrodes, where $\Delta\varphi_{\text{cathodic}}$ is found to be always larger than $\Delta\varphi_{\text{anodic}}$ within the applied voltage range, the situation is very different for Pt electrodes. As it is evident from Fig. 4a, $\Delta\varphi_{\text{cathodic}}$ under UHV conditions initially increases only very moderately in a linear trend (slope 0.12 V/V) up to 1.2 V applied voltage and then strongly increases with a slope of 0.81 V/V (black symbols); its absolute value stays always below the dashed line in the studied voltage range, that is, it is always smaller than $\Delta\varphi_{\text{anodic}}$. Indeed, we already observed for different imidazolium ILs that under UHV conditions, $\Delta\varphi_{\text{anodic}}$ generally is larger than $\Delta\varphi_{\text{cathodic}}$ for Pt electrodes (Greco et al., 2019). This asymmetric behavior at low voltages was attributed to the specific attractive interaction of the π ring orbital of the aromatic cation with the d orbitals of the Pt electrode (Greco et al., 2019).

To study the impact of ambient environment, we also measured $\Delta\varphi_{\text{cathodic}}$ curves in N_2 and air; the data are also shown in Fig. 4a (red and blue symbols, respectively). Up to 0.7 V, a similar PS behavior as in UHV is observed. In contrast, the transition to the steeper slope already

Fig. 4. a) Cathodic voltage of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ vs U_{applied} between two identical Pt electrodes. The black line refers to the measurements performed in UHV with XPS, red and blue lines refer to the measurements performed with a 3rd reference electrode in N_2 and Air atmosphere, respectively. The green line represents PS data of a 1 : 1 molar solution of water and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ recorded with a 3rd reference electrode in N_2 . The dashed straight line (± 0.5 V/V) indicates equal PS at the cathode and the anode. b) Averaged current recorded during the measurements.

occurs at 0.7 V in N_2 and air. This transition coincides with the onset of a significant current in Fig. 4b, which is absent in UHV under the otherwise same conditions. Due to the similarity of the PS curves, we propose that the ambient conditions hardly affect the EDLs up to 0.7 V. The deviations observed at higher voltages are attributed to a change in the composition of the EDLs, such that the electrode/liquid interfaces are not exclusively composed of the counterions of the IL, but also by additional species formed in the redox reactions at the electrodes, which change the composition of the EDL. It is tempting to speculate about the nature of the formed redox species: since atomic hydrogen is known to be strongly bound on Pt (Zhao et al., 2009, Vurdu, 2018), a possible candidate is hydrogen formed by reduction of residual water at the cathode, which weakens the specific attractive interaction of the imidazolium ring with the Pt electrode. As a consequence, the slope of the corresponding cathodic voltage curves changes more to the situation where the EDL capacitances are dominated by the different sizes of cation and anion without specific ion-electrode interactions in a similar way such as measured in the previous example of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ in contact with Au electrodes even for values of U_{applied} close to zero.

In order to verify that the observed effects under ambient conditions are indeed due to water (as already suggested above) we performed an additional measurement with high water content. The green symbols in Figs. 4a and 4b show $\Delta\varphi_{\text{cathodic}}$ and current values of a 1:1 molar mixture of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ and H_2O , that is, one water molecule per ion pair measured with Pt electrodes in 1 bar N_2 . While the PS is identical to the measurements of the pure IL in N_2 and air, the observed currents have significantly increased as compared to air and even more as compared to N_2 . This behavior strongly suggests that it is most likely water that leads to the observed deviations from ultraclean conditions. The fact that the changes in PS already occurred for N_2 , that is, with a molar ratio $\text{H}_2\text{O} : [\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl} = 1 : 9$ as determined by Karl Fischer titration, indicates that already small amounts of water are sufficient to change the EDL. Notably, the water content is expected to be much

Fig. 5. a) Cathodic voltage of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ vs U_{applied} between two identical Au electrodes. The black line refers to the measurements performed in UHV with XPS, red and blue lines refer to the measurements performed with a 3rd reference electrode in N_2 and Air atmosphere, respectively. The dashed straight line ($\pm 0.5 \text{ V/V}$) indicates equal PS at the cathode and the anode. b) Averaged current recorded during the measurements.

lower in the measurements performed with XPS in UHV in accordance with literature values of vacuum-dried $[\text{C}_n\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ and $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ ILs (O'Mahony et al., 2008). This expected much lower amount of dissolved water is also in line with the negligible steady-state current observed in UHV for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ in comparison to N_2 and air atmosphere with both Au and Pt electrodes (see Figs. 3b-4b).

The comparison of Au and Pt as electrode materials with the same IL shows how the interactions between ions, contaminants and electrodes strongly influence the observed PS, which is attributed to changes of EDL composition. These deviations observed above 0.7 V applied in N_2 and air, compared to UHV, can be relevant to electrochemical studies with a 3-electrode setup, such as CV and chronoamperometry. As mentioned above for a standard potentiostatic arrangement, the desired ΔV_{ref} is set between WE and RE and it is achieved by applying a voltage with a potential source between WE and CE. In this regard, different biases have to be applied between WE and CE in N_2 atmosphere and air than under ultraclean conditions.

$[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ Au/Au

While in the previous examples, cation and anion were very different in size, the sizes and thus also the expected EDL dimensions are very similar for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ as electrolyte. Fig. 5a depicts $\Delta\varphi_{\text{cathodic}}$ as function of applied voltage between two identical Au electrodes. The XPS-derived data in UHV (black symbols) reveal a linear behavior with a slope of 0.45 V/V, that is, they lie approximately on the ideal line for symmetric PS with $\Delta\varphi_{\text{cathodic}} = \Delta\varphi_{\text{anodic}}$. We attributed this behavior to the absence of pronounced specific chemical interactions between the Au electrode and the anions and cations of the IL; the EDL capacitances are thus given by the similar size of the counterions at the corresponding interfaces (Greco et al., 2019). The experiments performed in N_2 and in air (red and blue symbols, respectively) show the same PS behavior as in UHV, which indicates that ambient conditions do not significantly affect the structure of the EDL.

Fig. 6. a) Cathodic voltage of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ vs U_{applied} between two identical Pt electrodes. The black line refers to the measurements performed in UHV with XPS, red and blue lines refer to the measurements performed with a 3rd reference electrode in N_2 and Air atmosphere, respectively. The dashed straight line ($\pm 0.5 \text{ V/V}$) indicates equal PS at the cathode and the anode. b) Averaged current recorded during the PS measurements.

$[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ Pt/Pt

The cathodic voltage curve of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ measured for two identical Pt electrodes in UHV is depicted in Fig. 6a (black symbols). We observe the typical asymmetric behavior of imidazolium-based ILs on Pt electrodes described above, with $\Delta\varphi_{\text{cathodic}}$ being smaller than $\Delta\varphi_{\text{anodic}}$; the initial slope of the curve is 0.27 V/V. The PS curves recorded in N_2 and air (red and blue symbols, respectively), however, show a steeper increase with a slope of 0.44 V/V and 0.42 V/V respectively, which is closer to the ideal line. Similar to our observation on Au for this IL, the observed currents between WE and CE are very low for this electrolyte in UHV and also under non-UHV conditions up to 1.5 V applied, which rules out pronounced redox reactions being responsible for the observed changes. Hence, we attribute the different PS curves for Pt to the fact that residual contaminants being present in the IL (most likely traces of water) adsorb on Pt and weaken the interaction of the IL with the electrode; this in turn leads to different liquid/metal EDLs than in UHV.

Interestingly, the comparison of the observed behavior for Pt and Au electrodes shows a pronounced influence of the ambient conditions on the PS behavior for both $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ in case of Pt electrodes, while for Au electrodes hardly any influence is seen. We tentatively attribute these differences between Pt and Au electrodes to the hydrophobicity and ionophilicity of the Au electrode (Cheng et al., 2015), at which the interaction with water molecules is unfavorable over the ions of the IL. In contrast, the interactions between Pt electrodes and the imidazolium cations dominate for pure ILs, but under ambient conditions, the affinity of certain contaminants or redox products might be even stronger and drastically alter the interfacial composition.

Contamination of the 3rd reference electrode

In this section we want to address an interesting observation in some of our studies. Typically, we perform four PS measurements with

positive and negative U_{applied} voltage steps and either the WE or CE grounded. The four quadrants as shown in Fig. 2 are then averaged yielding the data shown in Figs. 3 to 6. The detailed measurements as a function of time are shown in Figs. S3 to S6. After a voltage ramp from 0 to ± 2 V, the applied voltage was set back to 0 V to start the next experiment. In all UHV experiments (black data), the ΔBE values and also in all experiments in N_2 the ΔV_{ref} values (red data) dropped back to zero, as is to be expected. This is also the case for the experiments in air (blue data), with the exception of the experiments for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ with Pt and Au electrodes, where we observe a strong change on the ΔV_{ref} at $U_{\text{applied}} = 0$ V (Figs. S5 and S6, blue data). This deviation was observed after the first voltage ramp in air, and it was persistent for all the following measurements. These deviations were not observed in UHV and N_2 and with all the other electrode/IL combinations in all the different measuring conditions.

To further investigate this phenomenon, we measured ΔV_{ref} for $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ with two identical Au electrodes at $U_{\text{applied}} = 0$ V for 10 minutes before and after positive and negative voltage steps (Fig. S7). For all U_{applied} values up to ± 1.5 V, the ΔV_{ref} value measured at $U_{\text{applied}} = 0$ V after the voltage steps approached zero after a certain relaxation time, indicative of the reorganization of the EDL after the potential change: For instance, for $U_{\text{applied}} = -1.5$ V, we observe a positive ΔV_{ref} during the step and after changing back to $U_{\text{applied}} = 0$ V, a small remaining positive ΔV_{ref} value slowly decays to zero. Accordingly, for $U_{\text{applied}} = +1.5$ V, ΔV_{ref} is negative, and after changing back to $U_{\text{applied}} = 0$ V, a small remaining negative ΔV_{ref} value slowly decays to zero. Surprisingly, the behavior is different when applying ± 2.0 V, where the ΔV_{ref} values recorded at $U_{\text{applied}} = 0$ V after the steps are always negative, independent of the sign of the voltage steps.

We attribute the expected behavior up to ± 1.5 V to the slow transport kinetics of the IL ions in the highly viscous media, leading to a slow reorganization of the counterions at the EDL after the potential step and an excess of cations at the cathode and anions at the anode remaining when no voltage is applied ($U_{\text{applied}} = 0$ V). It has been reported in differential capacitance (DC) measurements that slow transport kinetic can lead to hysteresis of the DC curves, which requires to wait until the system is back to equilibrium before starting a new measurement (Lockett et al., 2010).

In contrast, the always negative ΔV_{ref} values observed at $U_{\text{applied}} = 0$ V after ± 2.0 V steps in Fig. S7 have a different origin. We attribute them to redox products in the IL phase that adsorb on the 3rd reference electrode and thereby change the reference potential. As our setup is symmetric with respect to WE and CE, positive or negative applied voltages lead to the same redox products and thus the same effect on the 3rd reference electrode. A possible origin of this effect could be electrodegradation of the $[\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ anion in presence of OH^- and water, that is, when not operating in dry conditions (Howlett et al., 2006). This reaction produces anionic and radicalic fragments of the $[\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]^-$, such as $^-\text{NSO}_2\text{CF}_3^-$ and SO_2CF_3^- , which can be highly surface-active at the 3rd reference electrode.

As mentioned above, the 3rd reference electrode used in our study is related to the reference electrode of a standard 3-electrode setup. In this regard, our study shows the possibility to use the ΔBE recorded through XPS as a stable and reliable reading of the potential difference between the electrolyte and the electrodes. This is particularly interesting for all *in-situ* studies in which all the three electrodes (WE, CE and RE) are located in the same cell compartment and therefore, the influence of redox species on the stability of the RE cannot be avoided.

Finally, the observed sensitivity of the potential measured by the 3rd reference electrode towards contaminations could also be a hint towards explaining uncertainties/differences of several tenths of eV that are frequently observed in reported XPS binding energy values of nominally identical ILs (Villar-Garcia et al., 2011, Foelske-Schmitz et al., 2013). These can possibly be traced back to changes of the potential drop at the interface of the IL with the grounded support due to residual contaminations adsorbing at this interface, and thus, changing the related

EDL. Moreover, this interpretation could explain long-term changes of XPS binding energy values quite commonly observed during the course of XPS measurements, due to adsorption of species created by X-ray-induced beam damage of the ILs.

Conclusions

We investigated the effect of ambient conditions on the potential screening (PS) at the interface of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ with polarized Au and Pt electrodes. For this purpose, data collected in 1 bar air and also in 1 bar N_2 using a 3-electrode setup are compared to reference measurements under ultraclean (contamination-free) conditions by XPS in a symmetric 2-electrode setup. The observed binding energy shifts as a function of the applied voltage U_{applied} mirror the PS and EDL composition at the polarized electrode/IL interfaces. From the comparison, conclusions on the influence of contaminations on the PS can be derived: On the one hand, if the PS curves recorded in N_2 (that is, moderate clean conditions) or air (full ambient conditions) show the same behavior as in UHV, we can assume that contaminants from ambience do not have a significant effect on the PS. On the other hand, different PS curves arising from different measuring environments indicate an alteration of the PS by contaminations. In the course of our study, we first confirmed that PS measurements performed by XPS in UHV yield the same results as measurements using a very specific 3-electrode sample holder in UHV. This proof-of-principle experiment is the basis for comparing PS measurements by XPS in UHV with PS measurements with a 3-electrode setup performed in N_2 and in air. Additional information is obtained from simultaneously recording the cell current between working and counter electrode.

With our PS and current measurements, we demonstrate that there is indeed an influence of the gas atmosphere, which depends on applied voltage and the combination of IL and electrode material. For Pt electrodes, we find a pronounced influence of the ambient conditions on the PS for both $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$, while for Au electrodes hardly any influence is seen even under faradaic conditions. The latter indicates that due to overall attractive interactions between Au and IL ions, the EDLs are dominated by the IL counterions whereas other possible co-adsorbed species that are e.g. produced in a faradaic process have a short life-time at the metal-IL interface. In contrast, the very specific interactions between Pt electrodes and the imidazolium cations that dominate for pure ILs, are significantly altered under ambient conditions due to the affinity of certain contaminants or redox products adsorbing on Pt. These findings indicate that the interplay between contaminations, IL ions and the electrode material determine the composition of the EDL in which the strongest interactions lead to the final interfacial behavior. By adding an excess of water in a 1:1 water-IL solution, we demonstrated that the contamination effect on PS observed under ambient conditions is most likely due to water. In the course of our studies, we also observed that for certain IL/electrode combinations reaction products formed under faradaic conditions lead to a contamination of the 3rd reference electrode, yielding time-dependent deviations from the true behavior.

To conclude, our findings demonstrate that in electrochemical studies and applications of ILs in ambient conditions several factors can compromise the results and the performances of such devices. In this regard, the comparison between the PS behaviors obtained with *in-situ* XPS under ultraclean conditions and with the 3rd reference electrode in ambient conditions can be employed as a reliable tool to detect and subsequently avoid undesirable effects arising from species other than solely the ions of the ILs.

Experimental

$[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ were synthesized as reported in a previous publication (Kolbeck et al., 2009), and the amounts of water

estimated by Karl Fischer titration were 932.5 ppm and 9981.0 ppm respectively. After introducing the IL into the UHV chamber and degassing overnight, no contaminations like adventitious carbon, oxygen or silicon were detected by XPS. The Pt (\varnothing 0.30 mm) and Au (\varnothing 0.25 mm) electrodes were purchased from MaTeck with a purity of 99.99% and 99.995% and flame annealed before use.

To characterize the potential screening (PS) behavior in UHV using XPS, cathodic voltage values for both ILs with Au and Pt electrodes (data from (Greco et al., 2019)) were deduced from the changes in N 1s and F 1s binding energy positions of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$, respectively, as a function of the applied voltage U_{applied} (see Supporting Information, Figs. S8 – S11). U_{applied} was limited to ± 2 V to ensure non-faradaic conditions as demonstrated by chronoamperometry (for details, see (Greco et al., 2019)). The PS measurements recorded in N_2 atmosphere and air were performed in an air-tight box (see details in Supporting Information and Fig. S2) with an electrochemical cell developed by our group. The cell consists of a PEEK reservoir in which the IL is filled and WE and CE are immersed with great care to have the same contact area with the IL ($\pm 5\%$). The distance between WE and CE was 5 mm and the Pt 3rd reference electrode was placed in between them at a distance of 2.5 mm from each. WE and CE were connected to a Keithley 2450 used as potentiostat. The voltage profiles were recorded with a Keithley DMM6500 used as high resistance multimeter.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.jil.2022.100019.

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